

Properties and Reactions of Charge Transfer Excited States in Mono/Polynuclear Polypyridyl Complexes of Ru, Os and Re

K. KALYANASUNDARAM

Institute of Physical Chemistry, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

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Properties and reactions of different types of charge transfer excited states [metal-to-ligand (or MLCT), ligand-to-metal (or LMCT) and metal-to-metal (MMCT)] of mono- and polynuclear polypyridyl complexes of Ru, Os and Re are reviewed, with examples taken mostly from the work done in the authors' laboratory in the last decade. Properties and dynamical aspects of the CT transitions are deduced from ground state absorption, emission, transient absorption spectra, their lifetimes and acid-base behaviour. Possible ways of tuning of the energy of the CT transitions are discussed followed by features of photoredox reactions. Polynuclear complexes considered are bi- and trinuclear ones derived using bis(2-pyridyl)pyrazine (dpp) or cyanide as the bridging ligand. Properties of mixed valence compounds formed during chemical oxidation or optical excitation are indicated and also intramolecular energy and electron transfer reactions involving central and peripheral chromophores.

2,2'-Bipyridine (bpy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen)¹ and related polypyridine ligands are unique in their ability to complex to a large number of transition metal ions across the periodic table. The complexation equilibria and redox reactivity of these complexes have been the focus of experimental investigations for many years^{2–4}. Complexes of metal ions with d^6 electronic configuration are attractive from photophysical and photochemical properties point of view. The intense colour and photoreactivity of these complexes is due to low-energy charge transfer (CT) transitions. Polypyridyl complexes of Ru^{II} are the most widely studied ones^{5,6}. Extensive information is available on the dynamics of formation, decay and reactivity of electronically excited states of these complexes^{7–9}. Photochemical studies have also been extended¹⁰ to complexes of other d^6 ions such as Os^{II}, Fe^{II}, Rh^{III} and Ir^{III}. Information is also available¹⁰ on the polypyridine complexes of d^3 (e.g. Cr^{III} and V^{III}) and d^{10} ions (e.g. Cu^I).

Since mid-seventies we have been interested in the photochemistry of polypyridine complexes, partly to explore their excited state chemistry per se and partly to find possible applications in areas such

as photochemical conversion and storage of solar energy^{9–11}. Complexes containing dicarboxybipyridine as one of the ligands have been of particular interest, in connection with the development of efficient water oxidation catalysts^{12,13} and in photoelectrochemical sensitisation of large band semiconductors using visible light^{14–16}.

Fig. 1 shows schematically the relative dispositions of various molecular orbitals and associated electronic transitions in such complexes in a pseudo-octahedral ligand field. The electronically excited states correspond to transitions between various molecular orbitals derived from the ligand (π, π^*) orbitals and metal ($3d/4d$) orbitals. The excited state can be one of the following types: charge transfer (CT), metal-centered (MC, 1) and ligand-centered (LC, 2). As their names imply, metal-centered excited states involve electronic transitions amongst molecular orbitals that are essentially localised on the metal ion and ligand-centered ones involve transitions amongst MO's that ligand-localised. CT transitions involve promotion of an electron from a metal ion MO to one of ligand-based ones (case identified as MLCT, 3) or vice versa (LMCT, 4). The relative energy ordering of different electronic transitions

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the relative disposition of various metal and ligand-based molecular orbitals in polypyridine complexes with d^6 metal ions in pseudo-octahedral ligand field and associated electronic transitions : (1) $d-d$ (MC), (2) $\pi-\pi^*$ (LC), (3) $d-\pi$ (MLCT), (4) $\pi-d$ (LMCT)

depends on the nature of the polypyridine ligands, the metal ion and the ligand field strength. In polynuclear complexes with metal ions in different oxidation states there can be metal-to-metal (or intervalence) transitions as well. In this article we review some of the properties and reactions of these excited states.

The lowest energy transition is the most important one as the emission and photochemistry often occur from this excited state. Luminescence (also called emission) is the simplest and direct means of characterising an excited state. It can be observed in frozen glasses at low temperature and most often in fluid solutions as well. Luminescence in the steady state is the easiest to measure and the amount of information one can obtain is rather limited. Time-resolved measurements of the excited state either by emission or transient absorption are more attractive. The excited states of polypyridine complexes of Ru^{II} , Os^{II} and Re^I have lifetimes in the nanosecond timescales and hence studies of excited state require flash photolysis equipments that use short pulsed lasers as excitation source and related fast data

acquisition and analysis equipments. Fast kinetic spectroscopic methods allow monitoring of the absorption spectra of the excited state as well as products of electron or energy transfer.

MLCT excited states of polypyridine complexes

Amongst d^6 ions in an pseudo-octahedral field, the ligand field strength (Δ) increases along the series Fe, Ru, Os, Rh and Ir. The lowest energy transition consequently shifts from MC in Fe^{II} to MLCT in Ru^{II} , Os^{II} to LC in Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} . The excited state energy also increases along this series. In Ru^{II} and Os^{II} complexes, the CT transition [$(d^6_{\pi}) \rightarrow (d^5_{\pi})(\pi_{LL}^*)$] is emissive in fluid solutions and also shows extensive redox reactivity. Luminescence in the visible light region arising from low-lying MLCT excited state has been observed in a number of carbonyl polypyridine complexes with d^6 ions such as $[Re^I(CO)_3(LL)(X)]$ and $[M(CO)_4(LL)]$, $M = Cr(0)$, $Mo(0)$ and $W(0)$. The chemistry of MLCT excited states of these carbonyl polypyridyl complexes are very similar to those composed purely of polypyridines. Table 1 shows representative data on the properties of the lowest excited state in select transition metal polypyridyl complexes.

TABLE 1—EXCITED STATE PROPERTIES OF TRANSITION METAL POLYPYRIDYL COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT ROOM TEMPERATURE, $[M(LL)_n]^{m+}$ *

Compd	LL	Excited state	τ (ns)	E^* (eV)
$Fe(LL)_3^{3+}$, $3d^6$	bpy	MC	0.8	-0.9
	phen	MC	0.8	-0.9
$Ru(LL)_3^{2+}$, $4d^6$	bpy	MLCT	620	2.10
	phen	MLCT	920	2.12
$Os(LL)_3^{2+}$, $5d^6$	bpy	MLCT	19	1.85
	phen	MLCT	84	1.78
$Rh(LL)_3^+$, $4d^6$	phen	LC	44	2.80
$Ir(LL)_3^+$, $5d^6$	bpy	LC	2400	2.80
	phen	LC	2900	2.8
$Cr(LL)_3^3+$, $3d^3$	bpy	MC	77000	1.70
	phen	MC	270000	1.70
$V(LL)_3^3+$, $3d^3$	bpy	MLCT	1.8	≈ 1.4
	phen	MLCT	0.5	≈ 1.4
$Cu(LL)_2^+$, $3d^{10}$	dmp	MLCT	90	1.80

* Data taken from Refs. 5 and 10. For ligand abbreviations see Ref. 1

The major attractions for the Ru-complexes are the following : (i) intense CT absorption in the visible ($\lambda_{\text{max}} \approx 450\text{--}500$ nm, $\epsilon \approx 1\text{--}2 \times 10^4$ $M^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), (ii) moderately intense emission with fairly long lifetime in fluid solutions at ambient temperature ($\phi \approx 0.01\text{--}0.05$, $\tau \approx 0.5\text{--}2.0$ μs), (iii) high quantum yield for the formation of the lowest CT excited state ($\phi \approx 1$), (iv) solubility in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents and (v) redox reactivity and ease of tunability of redox properties. Os^{II} complexes have CT excited states that are lower in energy and short-lived.

As mentioned earlier, the charge transfer transition involves promotion of electron from the (d_{π}^6) core at the metal to the low-lying π^* acceptor levels of the polypyridine ligands LL (equation 1),

There have been extensive discussions in the literature as to whether the promoted electron resides exclusively on one of the three polypyridine ligands ('localised') or dispersed over the entire π -system of the three ligands ('delocalised' description). Electrochemical, transient absorption and resonance Raman spectroscopic studies have been brought in to provide the answers.

Fig. 2 shows the transient absorption spectra of two tris-chelates $[\text{Ru}(4,4'\text{-dcbpy})_3]$ and $[\text{Ru}(5,5'\text{-dcbpy})_3]$ recorded at 50 ns after laser pulse excitation in aqueous solutions at ambient temperature¹⁷. The transient absorption spectra are characterised by a distinct absorption with a maximum (≈ 380 nm for the 4,4'-derivative and ≈ 410 nm for the 5,5'-derivative) that corresponds to that of the reduced carboxybipyridine ligand ($\text{dcbpy}^{\bullet-}$).

For the 4,4'-derivative the maximum is slightly red-shifted upon protonation in the excited state. The transient spectra clearly show that in fluid solution the electron resides on one of the three bpy ligands but, no doubt, undergoes rapid intramolecular transfer among them.

Fig. 2. Transient absorption spectra corresponding to MLCT excited state of $\text{Ru}(4,4'\text{-dcbpy})_3$ and $\text{Ru}(5,5'\text{-dcbpy})_3$ in acetonitrile, recorded following short (ns) laser pulse excitation.

The polypyridine complexes show distinct emission at ambient temperature. The quantum yield of emission is not high (few percent) but sufficient for routine measurements. The decay of MLCT excited state in fluid solution is dominated by non-radiative processes. In non-radiative decay the excess energy is released to various vibrational modes of the complex and the solvent. It appears that most of the energy release is via seven ring stretching modes with lesser roles played by the low-frequency metal-ligand modes and the solvent. It has also been found¹⁸⁻²⁰ that the non-radiative decay constant is proportional to the energy gap between the excited state and ground states in a logarithmic manner ('energy gap law' equation 3),

$$\ln k_{\text{nr}} \propto \frac{(\gamma E)}{h\omega} \quad (3)$$

In this equation E is the energy gap between the

excited and ground states and $h\omega$ is the averaged vibrational spacing for the bpy-based ring stretching modes.

In a number of Ru^{II}-polypyridine complexes, metal-centered excited states have energies only slightly higher than that of the MLCT states and they can be populated efficiently by thermal excitation at room temperature. Such thermal populating of upper MC excited states can cause substitutional lability of the complex,

In fact when the energy gap is tuned in a series of mixed ligand complexes $[\text{Ru}(\text{LL})_n(\text{LL}')_{3-n}]^{2+}$ (LL = bpy, bpz, bpm,...)^{18,19}, the photosubstitution quantum yield has been found to vary substantially. Larger the energy separation between the two levels, lower is the substitution quantum yield. Going from Ru to Os, the increased ligand-field strength causes similar/higher energy separation and increased stability. Laser flash photolysis of $\text{Ru}(\text{bpz})_3^{2+}$ has shown that the ligand-loss following excitation of the complex to the electronically excited state is extremely rapid ($\leq \text{ns}$)²¹.

Tuning of the MLCT excited state

Tunability refers to the tailor-made synthesis of complexes with desired photophysical and redox properties and is an important feature in the photochemistry of transition metal polypyridyl complexes (for some representative examples, see refs. 22–24). Tunability can be achieved by one of the following ways : (i) introduction of peripheral substituents that are electron-donating or electron-withdrawing, (ii) replacing one of the polypyridine ligands by other ligands (non-chromophoric) and (iii) varying the nature of the polyimine ligand. A homologous, graded series of complexes can be synthesised based on type (i) and (ii) tuning and such a series can be very useful to establish the mechanism of quenching of excited states.

Approach (i) is the simplest. Peripheral substitution of bpy/phen ligands can cause considerable

shifts in the redox potentials without changing appreciably the MLCT excited state energies. Lin *et al.*²² used extensively such homologous series of complexes to assess the relative importance of electron and energy-transfer quenching mechanisms. Nearly identical energies of the excited state would render the rate of energy transfer pathway nearly constant but the electron transfer rates with a given acceptor/donor should reflect the differences in the driving force.

Approach (ii) is based on mixed ligand complexes containing one or two bpy/phen ligands and one or more ligands that are non-chromophoric (X). For complexes with CT excited states, it suffices to have one or two of the polypyridine ligands (LL) to have the required $\text{M} \rightarrow \text{LL}$ CT transition, e.g. $[\text{M}(\text{LL})_2\text{X}_4]$ or even $[\text{M}(\text{LL})\text{X}_4]$. Non-chromophoric ligands can be σ -donors, π -donors or π -acceptors and in these cases, there can be substantial shifting of the energy of the MLCT excited state. Electron-donating ligands increase the charge density at the metal center of Ru, Os or Re. The accompanying destabilisation raises the t_{2g} level causing a overall decrease in the energy of the MLCT transition. Larger energy gaps observed upon replacement of one of the bpy ligands by good back-bonding ligands such as CO can be explained in a similar manner

A number of studies have shown that in mixed ligand complexes, the lowest energy CT transition involves the ligand that is most easily reduced. Thus in complexes of the type $[\text{M}(\text{bpy})_n(\text{LL}')_{3-n}]$ ($n = 1, 2$) containing dcbpy and an electron-rich ligand LL, the lowest excited states involve Ru \rightarrow dcbpy CT. The ligand LL is a 'spectator' rather than a participant, as shown below for $[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{LL})]^{2+}$,

The spectator however influences the energy gap by destabilisation of the metal-based ($d\pi^5$) core by electronic donation. As LL becomes a better donor, the MLCT transition energy is decreased, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the tuning of the energy of the CT excited state in $[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{LL})]^{2+}$ using better electron-donating or non-chromophoric ligands (LL).

Using the above principle, extensive tuning in the energy of the Ru-dcbpy CT excited state has been obtained in complexes of the type $[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2\text{X}_2]$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{Y-bpy})]$, where X is a non-chromophoric ligand (e.g. Cl, CN,...) and Y-bpy is a 4,4'-disubstituted-2,2'-bipyridine²⁵. Table 2 presents data on the absorption, emission and redox properties of a series of mixed ligand complexes of the type, $[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{LL})]$ in aqueous alkaline solutions (pH \approx 11) at ambient temperature. The 'spectator' ligand LL is either non-chromophoric or substituted bpy/phen with donor substituents. In all these cases the lower LUMO is much higher than the π^* -level of the ligand dcbpy and hence the lowest excited state is Ru-dcbpy CT. Shifting

of the energy of the MLCT excited state has important consequences on the emission properties. In general, lowering of the energy is accompanied by decreased emission quantum yield and shorter lifetimes. Data of this kind have been quantitatively interpreted in terms of the 'energy gap law'. Meyer *et al.*¹⁸⁻²⁰ demonstrated this behaviour for the CT excited state of Ru^{II} , Os^{II} and Re^{I} complexes.

Replacement of a bpy in $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+}$ by electron-withdrawing groups decreases the effective charge density at the metal and this in turn causes an increase of the energy of the MLCT transition. Indelli *et al.*²⁶ demonstrated extensive tuning of the Ru-bpy CT transition using cyanide and methylisocyanide (CNMe) ligands in complexes of the type $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3\text{-nXY}]$, where $n = 1, 2$; X, Y = CN, CNMe. The emission maximum of the Ru-bpy CT transition occurs at 2.32, 2.59, 2.78 and 3.25 eV in the complexes $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{CN})_2$, $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{CN})$, $(\text{CNMe})_2\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})(\text{CNMe})_3^{3+}$ respectively. The luminescence lifetime also increases significantly along this series.

LC and MC excited states of polypyridyl complexes of Rh^{III}

The lowest energy excited state in the polypyridyl

TABLE 2—TUNING OF ENERGY OF THE LOWEST ENERGY CT EXCITED STATE IN $[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{LL})]$ COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS ALKALINE SOLUTION AT 293 K

Compd	λ_{max} abs (nm)	λ_{max} em (nm)	τ (ns)	ϕ cm	$E (M^+/M)$ (V)
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_3]^{4-}$	464	635	800	0.05	+1.56
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{BINAP})]^{2-}$	455	636	735	0.047	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{bpy})]^{2-}$	462	651	560	0.019	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{Me}_2\text{-bpy})]^{2-}$	474	655	485	0.033	+1.20
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{DMG})]^{2-}$	466	665	500	0.019	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(2\text{-COOpy})]^-$	490	712	84	0.0019	+0.78
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{TMEN})]^{2-}$	510	716	126	0.0038	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{BPE})]^{2-}$	500	716	30	0.005	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{DCDIphen})]^{2-}$	494	719	35	0.0015	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{Me}_2\text{BzIm})]^{2-}$	492	732	45	0.0075	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{DEA-bpy})]^{2-}$	506	732	40	0.0075	+0.58
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{DHphen})]^{2-}$	516	760	17	0.0002	
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	525	770	\approx 20	0.00025	+0.80
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	534	800	\approx 10	0.00074	+0.57
$[\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2(\text{phpy})]^{3-}$	560	865	\approx 2	0.00027	+0.27

*Ligand abbreviations used are listed under Ref. 1, data taken from Ref. 25.

complexes of Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} is generally of ligand-centered (LC) type. The properties of the LC state however are often perturbed by nearby metal-centered excited state. Even subtle modifications of the structure of the polypyridine ligand causes in inversion of the lowest energy excited state. The lowest excited state of $\text{Rh}(\text{bpy})_2^{3+}$, for example, is LC (both in alcohol glass at 77 K and in fluid solutions at ambient temperature). Introduction of methyl groups at 3,3'-position of 2,2'-bpy leads to dual emission from MC and LC states, as in $\text{Rh}(3,3'\text{-Me}_2\text{-bpy})_2^{3+}$. MC-emission is dominant at 77 K but LC-emission is enhanced relative to MC-emission in fluid solutions. The lowest excited state of $\text{Rh}(\text{terpy})_2^{3+}$ similarly is assigned to MC type²⁸. The lowest excited state of $\text{Ru}(\text{terpy})_2^{2+}$ is the same as in $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2^{2+}$.

In our studies on the polypyridine complexes based on the tetramine ligand dpp, we found²⁹ such variations in the nature of the lowest excited state of mixed ligand complexes of Rh^{III} : $[\text{Rh}(\text{dpp})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$, $[\text{Rh}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{dpp})_2(\text{bpy})]^{3+}$. Luminescence and transient absorption studies have shown that over the temperature range 77–293 K, the lowest excited state of $[\text{Rh}(\text{dpp})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$ is metal-centered (MC or dd). Fig. 4 shows the emission spectra of mixed ligand complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{dpp})_2(\text{bpy})]^{3+}$ in alcoholic glass at 77 K. The emission consists of one broad structureless band in the red and a structured high energy band in the 440–580 nm region. The former is typical of MC excited state and the latter from the $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ excited state. The emission is thus mixed. Lifetime studies indicate the two low-lying LC and MC excited state to be non-equilibrated in rigid alcoholic glasses. Only very weak (π,π^*) emission is observed in fluid solutions (293 K). Distinct transient absorption following short laser pulse excitation allows establishment of spectra and lifetimes of these excited states in fluid solutions at ambient temperature.

Using a series of mixed ligand complexes *cis*- $\text{Rh}(\text{phen})_2\text{XY}^{n+}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Y} = \text{CN}$, $n = 1$; $\text{X} = \text{Y} = \text{NH}_3$, $n = 3$; $\text{X} = \text{NH}_3$, $\text{Y} = \text{Cl}$, $n = 2$), Indelli

Fig. 4. Emission spectra in alcoholic glass of the mixed ligand complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{bpy})(\text{dpp})_2]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})]^{3+}$ at 77 K.

and Scandola³⁰ showed that it is possible to cross-over from MC to LC-emission in Rh^{III} complexes. The auxiliary ligands X and Y allow changing the energy of the MC state in a predictable way without substantially affecting that of the LC state. The chloro complex is a MC emitter, the dicyano complex is a LC-emitter and the diammine complex shows dual LC and MC emission.

Acid-base reactions in the ground and excited state

Acid-base properties of the coordinated ligands provide a direct measure of the interplay between the σ -donor strength and π -bonding properties in influencing the $d\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ CT transition. Few studies in this area have unambiguously shown that optical excitation of metal complexes alter significantly the acid-base equilibria involving protonatable-li-

2,3-Bis(2-pyridyl)pyrazine
(dpp)4,4'-Dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridine
(dcbpy)

gands³¹⁻³³. We have made a systematic study of the acid-base properties in the ground and excited state of Ru and Os complexes containing one or more of the following protonatable ligands^{17,34} : doubly bidentate ligand 2,3-bis(2-pyridyl)pyrazine (dpp) and isomeric dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridines (4,4'- and 5,5'-dcbpy).

In the mononuclear complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})]^{2+}$, one pyridyl and one pyrazinyl nitrogen centers coordinate to the metal center. Protonation of the extra nitrogen centers alters significantly the charge distribution within the ligand that the protonation can be readily monitored using the intense $M \rightarrow \text{dpp}$ CT band in the visible region. In $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})]^{2+}$, protonation in the ground state occurs only in concentrated acid solutions. Fig. 5 shows some representative absorption spectral changes that occur in concentrated H_2SO_4 solutions (H_0 changes from -0.05 to -7.34). Increase of solution acidity leads to distinct color changes of the solution from orange to pink and then to deep violet. The MLCT band red-shifts substantially (from 485 to 560 nm). Fig. 5 (bottom) shows typical titration curves (% absorbance change vs pH) for a few mixed ligand complexes. Quantitative analysis of the absorption growth at 561 nm for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})]^{2+}$ shows one inflection point ($\text{p}K_a$) at -3.7 .

The free ligand dpp shows two $\text{p}K_a$ values 2.90 and 0.80 corresponding to protonation of the two pyridyl N-centers. The shift in the ground state $\text{p}K_a$ upon chelation of dpp to Ru^{II} , $\Delta\text{p}K_a$, of over

Fig. 5. (Top) Absorption spectral changes accompanying protonation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})]^{2+}$; curves 0-6 correspond to solutions of increasing acidity. (Bottom) Titration curves (% absorbance vs H_0) for three Ru complexes : $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{bpm})^{2+}$, $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpp})^{2+}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{dpp})_3^{2+}$.

6 $\text{p}K_a$ units is very significant. The low $\text{p}K_a$ value also suggests that the protonation occurs at the pyrazinyl N para to that coordinated to Ru.

The dpp complexes are moderately emissive in aqueous solutions at ambient temperature. Above pH 7.0, the emission is pH-independent. Emission intensity however varies significantly with pH in acidic solutions. The emission intensity decreases rapidly in mildly acidic solutions and no detectable emission is observed in 1M acid solutions. Quantitative analysis of the emission intensity vs pH indicates involvement of a single protonation step,

TABLE 3—DATA ON THE GROUND AND EXCITED STATE ACID-BASE EQUILIBRIA AND EMISSION PROPERTIES (pH 7, 293 K) FOR VARIOUS POLYPYRIDINE COMPLEXES OF Ru^{II} AND Os^{II*}

Complex	Ground state		Excited State		Emission (pH 7) Max (nm) and τ (ns)
	pK_a^* (1)	pK_a^* (2)	pK_a^* (1)	pK_a^* (2)	
[Ru(4,4'-dcbpy) ₃] ⁴⁺	2.20	1.70	4.60	1.75	625 (700)
[Ru(4,4'-dcbpy) ₂ (bpy)] ²⁺	2.50	1.80	4.40	1.75	625 (664)
[Ru(4,4'-dcbpy)(bpy) ₂]	2.85	1.75	4.25		638 (395)
[Ru(5,5'-dcbpy) ₃] ⁴⁺	2.80		3.80	1.80	665 (37)
[Os(4,4'-dcbpy) ₃] ⁴⁺	1.70		3.75	1.75	780 (≈30)
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (dpp)] ²⁺	-3.8		2.85		690 (127)
[Ru(dpp) ₃] ²⁺	-4.8		1.75		625 (270)
[Os(dpp) ₃] ²⁺	-4.6		2.45		767

*Data taken from Ref. 17; emission lifetime shown in parenthesis.

For [Ru(bpy)₂(dpp)]²⁺ the excited state pK_a^* , pK_a^* is determined to be 2.85. Comparison of the ground and excited state pK_a values (equations 6 and 7) shows that in the excited state the tetraimine complex is considerable more basic ($\Delta pK_a \approx 6$ pH units). Interestingly even larger ΔpK_a change (≈ 8 pH units) upon optical excitation is observed in the homo tris-chelate Ru(dpp)₃²⁺. Table 3 presents a summary of the acid-base dissociation constants in the ground and excited state measured for several Ru and Os complexes.

The pH-dependence of the bis- and tris-dcbpy complexes of Ru^{II} and Os^{II} is slightly different from those of the dpp-complexes. The emission is pH-independent above pH 7. Lowering of solution pH below 7 causes a sigmoidal decrease of intensity upto pH 3–4, the emission intensity then increases again, reaching to values about 70–80% of that observed at pH ≥ 7 . Thus the protonated form of the dcbpy complexes also have appreciable emission quantum yields. Two pK_a^* values corresponding to successive protonation of the dcbpy ligand can be determined (≈ 4.7 and 1.8 for Ru). Quantitative studies indicate that two protons are involved in each of these equilibria,

Crutchley *et al.*³² observed the emission intensity of Ru(bpz)₃²⁺ to recover significantly in highly acidic solutions and a similar behaviour is expected for the dpp complexes.

In principle, the inflection point, denoted as pK_a^* , derived from the emission intensity curves needs to be corrected for the differences in the excited state lifetime of the unprotonated (τ) and protonated (τ') forms according to the equation :

$$pK_a^{*'} = pK_a^* - \log(\tau/\tau') \quad (9)$$

Absence of any detectable emission in acidic solutions does not permit determination of lifetime τ' and hence absolute pK_a^* values. Several empirical methods have been described in the literature for the calculation of the excited state pK_a values from the absorption and emission spectra. In one such method (based on the Förster cycle³⁵), the excited state pK_a , pK_a^* , is calculated from the ground state pK_a and the equation,

$$pK_a^* = pK_a + 0.00209 (v_B - v_{BH^+}) \quad (10)$$

In the above equation v_B and v_{BH^+} refer to the maxima (in wavenumber) of the absorption of the basic and acidic forms. For [Ru(bpy)₂(dpp)]²⁺ and Ru(dpp)₃²⁺, the pK_a^* values calculated using the above equation (2.95 and 1.75) are in reasonable agreement with the apparent pK_a values (pK_a^*) determined from the emission titration curves. Given the limitations of such calculations, the agreement is satisfactory.

Two possible mode of electron distribution in the excited complex has been discussed in the literature : a localised description in which the promoted electron resides in one of the three diimine

ligand, and a delocalised description in which the electron density is equally distributed amongst the three diimine ligands. Substantial ΔpK_a value observed in the tris chelate $Ru(dpp)_3^{3+}$ is in agreement with the localised description of the MLCT excited state.

LMCT transitions in Ru^{III} and Os^{III} complexes with donor ligands

The Ru^{III} and Os^{III} complexes (octahedral, low-spin, with d^5 electronic configuration) in general show ligand-to-metal ($\pi_L \rightarrow t_{2g}^*$) charge transfer (LMCT) transitions in the visible light region. Much less is known on the LMCT states of these complexes³⁶⁻³⁹, possibly due to their very weak intensities ($\epsilon \leq 500 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) in the widely studied complexes $Ru(bpy)_3^{3+}$, $Os(bpy)_3^{3+}$ and their non-emissive nature. Two key investigations of electronic spectra are those of Bryant and Ferguson³⁷ and of Kober and Meyer³⁸.

Generally, low energy LMCT transitions are favourable when the metal oxidising and the ligand reducing. Thus it is reasonable to expect Ru^{III} and Os^{III} complexes with donor substituents at the 4,4'-

position of 2,2'-bipyridine ligand to show fairly intense ligand-to-metal CT bands. In fact the LMCT transitions in these complexes have been found⁴⁰ to be an order of magnitude more intense than that observed in the parent/unsubstituted bpy complex! Fig. 6 shows the absorption spectral changes observed upon oxidation of two diamino-bpy complexes, $[Ru(DA-bpy)_3]^{2+}$ and $[Ru(bpy)_2(DA-bpy)]^{2+}$ using bromine as the oxidant. The decrease in the MLCT absorption of the Ru^{II} species (max. in the 450–550 nm region) is accompanied by a concomitant growth of LMCT absorption in the red. Isosbestic points can be clearly observed. The electron donating capacity of the bpy is greatly enhanced in these complexes with substituted bpy ligands that the $M(II) \rightarrow M(III)$ oxidation occurs readily in solution ($E_{3+/2+} \leq 0.5 V$).

The properties of such LMCT bands have been examined⁴⁰ by a systematic tuning of the donor strength of the bipyridine ligand using different substituents (structures shown below). Results for a number of homo tris- and mixed ligand complexes (about twenty with the two metal ions) allow rationalisation of the observed trends in the energy

TABLE 4—DATA ON THE REDOX POTENTIALS, ENERGIES AND INTENSITIES OF LOW ENERGY LMCT TRANSITIONS IN POLYPYRIDINE COMPLEXES OF Ru^{III} AND Os^{III} IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Compd	σ_{p+}	$E_{ox.}$ (V) (III/II)	LL-M(III) CT	
			$\lambda_{max}(nm), \epsilon (M^{-1}cm^{-1})$	
$Ru(DMA-bpy)_3$	-1.7	0.15	683(5 820)	580(4 365)
$Ru(DA-bpy)_3$	-1.3	0.35	653(4 390)	526(3 160)
$Ru(DOH-phen)_2(DA-bpy)$	-1.05	0.50	809(3 800)	676(2 850)
$Ru(DA-bpy)_2(bpy)$	-0.87	0.60	725 ^a (4 300)	594(4 520)
$Ru(DMO-bpy)_3$	-0.78	0.80	730(5 150)	565(3 150)
$Ru(DO11-phen)_2(bpy)$	-0.61	0.90	973(4 060)	658(3 435)
$Ru(DA-bpy)(bpy)_2$	-0.43	0.95	746(3 410)	596(2 860)
$Ru(DMO-bpy)(bpy)_2$	-0.26	1.05	841(2 160)	690(560)
$Ru(DM-bpy)_3$	-0.31	1.10	642(480)	555(250)
$Ru(bpy)_3$	0	1.26	675(750)	
$Os(DMA-bpy)_3$	-1.7	-0.16	590(6 290)	513(5 705)
$Os(DA-bpy)_3$	-1.3	0	527(5 350)	465(5 795)
$Os(DMA-bpy)_2(DM-bpy)$	-1.23	0.10	648(5 210)	562(6 510)
$Os(DMA-bpy)_2(bpy)$	-1.10	0.15	666(4 850)	565(4 565)
$Os(DA-bpy)_2(DM-bpy)$	-0.97	0.25	586(3 210)	508(3 700)
$Os(DFO-bpy)_3$	-0.80	0.32	560	
$Os(DMO-bpy)_3$	-0.78	0.385	480	
$Os(DM-bpy)_2(DA-bpy)$	-0.64	0.40	596(3 830)	508(3 480)
$Os(DM-bpy)_3$	-0.31	0.60	536(603)	
$Os(bpy)_3$	0	0.85	563(585)	436(10 700)

Fig. 6 Absorption spectral changes observed during oxidation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{DA-bpy})_3]^{2+}$ (bottom panel) and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{DA-bpy})]^{2+}$ by bromine water in aqueous solution at ambient temperature.

and intensity of LMCT transitions. Table 4 presents data on the redox and absorption spectral properties of a number of Ru^{III} complexes.

R = H	(bpy)
R = Me	(DM-bpy)
R = OMe	(DMO-bpy)
R = NH_2	(DA-bpy)
R = NMe_2	(DMA-bpy)

Examination of the data presented in Table 4 reveals useful trends in the energy and intensities of the LMCT transitions: (i) the lowest energy LMCT transition of the tris-chelates $\text{M}(\text{LL})_3^{2+}$, is observed within a narrow range of 1.80 ± 0.1 eV for Ru^{III} and 2.20 ± 0.1 eV for Os^{III} in spite of the wide variation of $E_{3+/2+}$ values, (ii) in mixed ligand chelates, the LMCT transition occurs at lower energies than in the homo tris-chelates; this can

be seen clearly in the absorption spectra shown in Fig. 6, (iii) the intensity of the LMCT transition increases with decreasing values of the redox potential, $E[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}]$. The first point is reminiscent of the near isoenergetic MLCT transition observed in $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{bpyz})_3^{2+}$ complexes. In the latter complex, 0.5 V anodic shift of the E_{ox} is accompanied by similar shifts in the first oxidation.

The LMCT transitions involve electronic transitions between donor orbitals that are largely $\pi(\text{X-bpy})$ in character to acceptor orbitals that are largely d_{π} in character. With increasing electron donating character of the substituent X, the electron donating ability of the $\pi(\text{X-bpy})$ orbitals is enhanced and this effect is transmitted to the metal d_{π} -orbitals by via d_{π} - $\pi(\text{LL})$ mixing. The oxidation potential data shows that there is a corresponding ease of oxidation of the metal center from +2 to +3 state. This arises from a decrease in the π - d_{π} backbonding which makes the metal more electron-rich. Interestingly, the effect on the d_{π} -orbitals is nearly the same as in the π -orbitals even though the substituent changes are made in the ligand. The range of E_{ox} values for the $\text{M}(\text{II/III})$ couples (X = NMe_2 to H) is ≈ 1.0 V.

The above qualitative discussion of substituent effects on energy levels can be put on a quantitative basis using Hammett substituent values for various substituents employed⁴¹. Hammett substituent constant $\sigma_{\text{p}+}$ can be used as a measure of the relative donor strength of the substituted bpy ligand. (Correlations use $\sigma_{\text{p}+}$ instead of σ_{p} , for the latter values are more applicable for the cases where the substituent group interacts with the developing positive charge). To a first approximation, the energy of the acceptor t_{2g} orbital can be estimated using the first oxidation potential, $E[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}]$. For a collection of 20 Ru and Os complexes very good linear correlation can be observed between the first oxidation potential and the Hammett substituent constant $\sigma_{\text{p}+}$.

Energy of the ligand π -level can be calculated from the observed LMCT absorption maxima and the estimates of the acceptor t_{2g} level based on

the first oxidation potential. Here again there is excellent correlation of the ligand π -level with the donor strength of the ligand as given by σ^+ . The ligand π -level increases linearly with increasing donor strength. The parallel shift in the donor and acceptor levels account for near-isoenergetic values of the lowest energy LMCT transition. The red-shifted nature of the LMCT transitions in mixed ligand complexes can also be explained in a similar manner.

Photoredox reactions and their applications

Formation of an electronically excited state involves formation of an oxidised metal and radical-anion character to the ligand π -system and this confers the excited state with enhanced oxidising and reducing properties compared with the ground state. For this reason, the complexes undergo electron transfer reactions in the excited state with a number of electron donor and acceptor molecules. Focussing attention on the excited state metal complex, photoredox reactions in which the complex is oxidised is identified as 'oxidative quenching',

Similarly reactions such as those shown in which the complex is reduced (equation 12) are called 'reductive quenching',

Along with these electron-transfer quenching pathways, mention must also be made of 'energy transfer' (equation 13) processes in which the excitation energy is transferred from the excited state of the polypyridyl complex to some low-lying electronic state of the quencher,

The redox potentials for the excited state to act as an oxidant or reductant have been deduced from an analysis of the dependence of the quenching rate constants as a function of the redox potential of the quencher. The inter-relationships of ground and excited state potentials and the excited state energy are best illustrated in Latimer-type diagrams such as the one shown in Fig. 7 for $Ru(bpy)_3^{2+}$

Fig. 7 Schematic representation of the ground and excited state redox potentials in two equivalent representations for $Ru(bpy)_3^{2+}$

There are two principal approaches to study excited state quenching of metal complexes: (i) Stern-Volmer type analysis of the quenching efficiency for various quenchers and (ii) direct observation of the absorption spectra of redox products in flash photolysis experiments. In the first approach which is a steady-state method, quenching by a series of structurally related quenchers (with graded series of redox potential or excited states that can act as acceptors) is employed. Procedures for quantitative analysis (of the kinetic and thermodynamic data) are available that allow differentiation of one pathway from other. Numerous studies of photoredox reactions of polypyridine complexes have been made in the last decade. Ability to measure rate constants and yields of electron transfer reactions as a function of the driving force allow these systems ideal candidates to examine theories of electron transfer reactions of molecules, particularly those of Marcus, Hush and Weller⁴²⁻⁴⁵. Comprehensive reviews of photoredox reactions of polypyridine complexes are available^{9,46,47} and only some of their applications will be highlighted here.

Processes such as photodecomposition of water to molecular hydrogen and oxygen and photoreduction of CO_2 immediately come as potential candidates to examine:

Enormous interest shown on the photochemistry of transition metal polypyridyl complexes in fact is linked to this type of applications in the domain

of photochemical conversion of solar energy. Practically every metal complex with fully or partially characterised electronically excited state has been examined as a means of generating key oxidants and/or reductants required and some have shown partial success. A number of reviews of these topics are available^{11,12,48} and hence only the basic principles and summary of progress in these areas will be indicated.

Catalytic schemes for the photodecomposition of water, for example, consist essentially of two steps : (i) light-induced generation of strong oxidants (S^+) and reductants (Q^-) upon absorption of visible light by the sensitiser S ,

and (ii) redox catalytic decomposition of water using photogenerated species and suitable catalyst materials,

Since the electronically excited states of metal complexes are good oxidants and reductants it is possible to envisage several redox schemes to achieve one or more of the above processes.

For the above reactions to occur spontaneously at reasonable rates, the photogenerated reactants Q^- and S^+ satisfy certain thermodynamic requirements. Water reduction to molecular hydrogen in neutral aqueous solutions (pH 7) require $E [Q/Q^-] \geq -0.42$ V (vs NHE). Similarly on the water oxidation side, $E[D^+/D] \geq 0.80$ V (vs NHE). In reality, requirements are slightly higher as these reactions involve multi-electron transfer and have high over voltages even in the presence of suitable redox catalysts. In the case of tris(bipyridine)ruthenium with $E[Ru^{2+/+}] = -1.26$ V, $E[Ru^{3+/2+}] = +1.26$ V, $Ru(bpy)_3^{2+}$ is a good candidate for water reduction and $Ru(bpy)_3^{3+}$ a good one for water oxidation.

Attempts to carry out these processes simultaneously did not have much success, mainly due to problems of rapid back-reaction between the photogenerated reactants and even cross-reactions in multicomponent systems. For this reason attention

was focussed on photocatalytic schemes where either water oxidation or reduction is carried out. A third component is added that will rapidly regenerate the photosensitiser rapidly so that the system becomes photocatalytic. Fig. 8 shows schematically two such

Fig 8 Photocatalytic schemes for the sensitised photo-reduction (top) and photo-oxidation of water (bottom) using redox catalysts

approaches. In such partial systems it is inevitable that one of the components be oxidised (electron donor in the case of water reduction) or reduced (electron acceptor in cases of water oxidation) irreversibly. In principle, reversible electron donors and acceptors can be used but cross-reactions (as observed in systems for cyclic water cleavage) dominate under steady state conditions and overall yields of required products become negligible.

A number of electron acceptors have been identified for reaction (17) that can effectively mediate H_2 evolution from water in the presence of Pt-group based redox catalysts. Typical examples are bipyridinium salts such as methyl viologen (MV^{2+}), polypyridine complexes of Rh^{III} , Co^{II} and cage complexes of Co^{II} . For this reason, the oxidative quenching (reaction 11) of various transition metal polypyridine complexes, $[M(LL)_3]^{n+}$ by these electron acceptors have been extensively studied.

The reduced form of these quenchers (Q^-) have

enough reducing power to reduce water to molecular hydrogen and in fact they do so efficiently in the presence of suitable redox catalysts (reaction 17). A large number of bipyridinium salts corresponding to a wide range of redox potentials are known. The reduced forms of these viologen salts are deep blue in colour and quantitative details of their formation can be determined using laser flash photolysis techniques⁴⁹. The cage escape yield for the viologen radical has been determined and typical yields (ϕ) are 0.17 and 0.25 for the benzyl- and methyl viologen respectively. The cage escape yield is also strongly dependent on the ionic strength of the medium and this can be explained in terms of primary and secondary 'salt effects' on reactions involving ionic species⁵⁰.

A number of rhodium(III) complexes can be used effectively in place of viologens as relays. Thus photolysis of a solution containing $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+}$ as the photosensitiser, ascorbate as the electron donor and $[\text{Rh}(\text{dpm})_3\text{Cl}]^{3-}$ (dpm = diphenylphosphinobenzene-*m*-sulphonate) as the electron relay leads to net formation of hydrido-rhodium species via a reductive quenching cycle. Such hydrido-rhodium(II) or rhodium(I) complexes can also be generated by ligand-field photolysis of polypyridine complexes of Rh^{III} in the presence of electron donors such as triethanolamine. H_2 evolution from water occurs catalytically⁵¹.

Popular schemes for the photooxidation of water involve oxidative quenching of $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+}$ by electron acceptors that irreversibly decompose upon reduction. Typical electron acceptors of this kind are Co^{III} complexes (such as $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{2+}$, $\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)^{3-}$, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, Ti^{3+} and Ag^+). Reactions (19) to (21) take place following visible light irradiation^{52,53},

Catalysis of evolution of molecular oxygen from water can be achieved in the presence of homo-

geneously dispersed ions such as Fe^{III} , Mn^{II} or Co^{II} or using heterogeneously dispersed metal oxides such as RuO_2 or IrO_2 (dispersed in the form of powder, colloids or as solid samples)^{52,55}. The redox catalytic step (reaction 21) alone has been tested using $\text{Fe}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+}$. The yield of O_2 can be nearly quantitative under certain optimal conditions. These photoredox reactions can also be carried out in photoelectrochemical cells^{56,57}. Using appropriate catalytic electrodes (RuO_2 for O_2 evolution) and membrane separators, it is possible to spatially separate the zone where catalysis takes place from the zone where photoredox reactions take place.

Several light-induced electron transfer cycles using transition metal polypyridyl complexes that lead to catalytic fixation of CO_2 or CO have been identified⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰. Visible light photolysis of CO_2 -saturated aqueous acetonitrile solutions containing $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$ (as photosensitiser), Co^{II} ions (as the catalyst), 4,7- Me_2 -phenanthroline (as the ligand to complex the Co^{II} in situ), triethanolamine (as donor) yields a mixture of CO and H_2 (synthetic gas). The syn gas mixture is produced by simultaneous occurrence of two reductions,

Fig. 9 outlines the sequence of key electron transfer steps involved in the photocatalytic scheme.

Fig. 9. A light-induced redox catalytic scheme for the reduction of CO_2 using $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$ as the photocatalysts and Co^{II} complexes as mediators.

A slight variation of the above photochemical reduction scheme utilises $\text{Re}(\text{I})\text{CO}_3(\text{LL})\text{X}$, $\text{X} = \text{bpy}$, phen or their substituted derivatives and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br as the photoactive species. Amines have been shown to be efficient quenchers of the CT

excited state of Re^I complexes, $[\text{Re}(\text{CO})_3(\text{LL})(\text{X})]$, $\text{X} = \text{Br}, \text{Cl}^{61,62}$,

Formation of redox products have been observed in laser photolysis studies. The reduction is fully reversible with aromatic amines but is irreversible with aliphatic amines such as triethylamine TEA. It is known that the one-electron oxidation product $\text{TEA}^{+\bullet}$ rapidly deprotonates and the resulting radicals, being good reducing agents can reduce another molecule of the Re-complex. The reduced Re-complex is a labile specie. In the absence of rapid oxidation as in the back-reaction following light-induced electron transfer, it loses halide ion, generating a highly reactive intermediate capable of interacting directly with CO_2 . In fact a number of artificial systems that can effect overall reduction of CO_2 and CO based on Re^I complex have been discovered recently,

Photochemistry of polynuclear complexes

An attractive approach to increase the visible light response of metal complexes is by linking several chromophoric units with appropriate bridging ligands. There has been a growing interest in the design of such 'supramolecular assemblies'^{63,64}. Fig. 10 illustrates the concepts involved in the design

Fig. 10. Schematic representation of light harvesting in multi-chromophoric sensitizers and excited state charge injection of TiO_2 .

of 'antenna-sensitiser' systems employed in dye-sensitised photoelectrochemical cells. A polynuclear assembly is constructed using different chromophores (labelled A, B and C in the figure) each absorbing visible light in different regions and appropriate bridging ligands. In our studies of sensitisation of TiO_2 -electrodes one of these chromophoric units (B) carried a carboxylic group that interacts efficiently with the TiO_2 surface. Energy absorbed by the peripheral units (A, C) transfer excitation energy to the central chromophore B. The efficiency of light harvesting in such systems depends on the unidirectional flow of incident light energy. The nature of the bridge and the mode of linkage in these complexes influence strongly communication ('electronic coupling') between the constituent units.

The trinuclear complex $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{CN})\text{Ru}-\text{CN}-\text{Ru}(\text{dcbpy})_2-\text{NC}-\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{CN})]$ (structure shown) is a representative case where efficient sensitisation of the TiO_2 has been observed recently^{15,16,65}. The acceptor character of the carboxyl groups renders the central chromophore lowest in energy. The light harvesting process in the present case would involve efficient channelling of high-energy photons via transfer of the excitation energy from the peripheral units to the central Ru-dcbpy based CT excited state. This is indicated by uniformly high charge injection efficiencies observed over the entire absorption spectral range of the trinuclear complex.

MLCT transitions in tetraimine bridged polynuclear complexes

Recently there have been a number of studies

of photophysics and intramolecular energy/electron transfer reactions of supramolecular assemblies derived using different bridging ligands. We⁶⁶⁻⁷⁰ and others⁷¹⁻⁷³ examined polynuclear complexes composed of polypyridine units linked together by the doubly bidentate ligand 2,3-bis(2-pyridyl)pyrazine (dpp). Shown below are the structures of some the binuclear complexes derived using the ligand, dpp. In addition to homo-binuclear complexes of the type $[\text{Ru}(\text{LL})_2]_2(\text{dpp})^{4+}$ (LL = bpy, biq), we also examined hetero-binuclear complexes, such as $[(\text{bpy})_2\text{Ru}-\text{dpp}-\text{M}(\text{bpy})_2]^{n+}$, M = Os^{II}, Rh^{III} and $[(\text{bpy})_2\text{Ru}-\text{dpp}-\text{Re}(\text{CO})_3(\text{Cl})]$.

One of the dpp-based binuclear complexes examined⁶⁷ was an asymmetrically substituted one, viz. $[(\text{bpy})_2\text{Ru}-\text{dpp}-\text{Ru}(\text{biq})_2]^{4+}$. In this complex, there are three CT transitions involving Ru^{II} and each of the three polypyridine ligands: Ru → bpy, Ru → biq and Ru → dpp. Electrochemical data often allow identification of the lowest energy transition, for the ligand that is most easily reduced, is the one having the lowest energy excited state. Amongst the three, 2,2'-bpy is the most difficult one to reduce and hence the CT transition involving bpy is the highest in energy. Absorption spectral and electrochemical data however do not allow differentiation of the two other CT transitions. In dpp-based binuclear complexes, the bridging ligand reduction occurs at ≈ -0.7 V, a value lying in the range expected for biq-based reductions.

However, by monitoring the resonance enhancement of the Raman bands during excitation within

the lowest energy absorption band, it is possible to identify clearly the lowest energy CT transition in the binuclear complex⁷⁰. Fig. 11 shows the

Fig. 11. Resonance Raman spectra of dpp-bridged binuclear Ru-complexes: $[(\text{biq})_2\text{Ru}-\text{dpp}-\text{Ru}(\text{biq})_2]^{4+}$ with excitation at (A) 530.9 nm and (B) 568.2 nm, and (C) of $[(\text{bpy})_2\text{Ru}-\text{dpp}-\text{Ru}(\text{biq})_2]^{4+}$ with excitation at 568.2 nm.

resonance Raman spectra of the binuclear complex in question at two excitation wavelengths and also that of the binuclear complex $[(\text{biq})_2\text{Ru}-\text{dpp}-\text{Ru}(\text{biq})_2]^{4+}$. The marker bands of 2,2'-biquinoline (biq) are at 1070, 1173, 1253, 1344, 1373, 1463 and 1559 cm^{-1} . The marker bands of dpp are at 1186, 1243, 1310, 1395, 1474, 1551 and 1598 cm^{-1} . A careful examination of the spectra reveals that the Raman spectrum of the mixed ligand complex obtained with low energy excitation (568 nm) consists

TABLE 5—PHOTOPHYSICAL AND REDOX PROPERTIES OF MONO- AND POLYNUCLEAR COMPLEXES BASED ON THE TETRAIMINE LIGAND dpp IN CH₃CN (or DMF) AT ROOM TEMPERATURE*

Compd	λ _{max} abs (nm)	λ _{max} em (nm)	τ (ns)	E(M ⁺ /M) (V)	E(M/M ⁻) (V)
[Ru(bpy) ₂ (dpp)] ²⁺	468,434	682	382	+1.34(Ru)	-1.14 (dpp)
[Ru(bpy) ₂] ₂ (dpp) ⁴⁺	526,424	790	140	+1.38(Ru)	-0.71 (dpp)
[Os(bpy) ₂ (dpp)] ²⁺	578,486	808	60	+0.85(Os)	-1.05 (dpp)
[Os(bpy) ₂] ₂ (dpp) ⁴⁺	719,520	>850		+0.83(Os)	-0.72 (dpp)
Re(CO) ₃ (Cl)(dpp)	418	625	50	+1.33(Re)	-1.05 (dpp)
[(CO) ₃ (Cl)Re] ₂ (dpp)	486	790	≤20	+>1.4(Re)	-0.69 (dpp)
[Os(bpy) ₂ -dpp-Re(bpy) ₂] ²⁺	692,534	>850		+0.90(Os)	-0.73 (dpp)
Re(CO) ₃ (Cl)-dpp-Ru(bpy) ₂	512	770		+>1.34(Re)	-0.66 (dpp)
[Rh(bpy) ₂ -dpp-Ru(bpy) ₂] ²⁺	514	778	37	+1.34(Ru)	-0.65 (dpp/Rh)

*Data taken from Ref. 21

essentially resonance-enhanced biq bands. Thus the lowest energy excited state in the complex [(biq)₂Ru-dpp-Ru(biq)₂]⁴⁺ involves Ru-biq CT. Unambiguous assignment of the lowest excited state in polynuclear complexes are by no means trivial. The assignment of the lowest excited state as CT transition involving peripheral/spectator units has important implications in the working of light-harvesting devices based on these units.

Table 5 presents representative data on the absorption emission and redox properties of some dpp-based complexes. A common feature of this class of compounds is that in going from mononuclear to binuclear species, an anodic shift (≈ 350 mV) in the reduction potential is observed. There is substantial energy stabilisation of the bridge π*-orbitals upon binucleation. A parallel red-shift of the M-BL CT transition is observed in the absorption as well as in the emission spectrum. The emission from the binuclear complex is much weaker and shorter-lived, a behaviour expected on the basis of the energy gap law. There have been extensive discussions in the literature on the extent of electronic coupling between the two metals in this type of complexes. Petersen *et al.*⁷² proposed the shift in the oxidation potential of the binuclear complex with respect to the mononuclear one and the comproportionation constant, K_{comp} (equation 26) as a measure of the communication between the metal centres,

For dpp-complexes the difference in the oxidation potential (ΔE) is very small, indicating a weak metal-metal interaction

The excited states of the two chromophoric units {M₁(LL)₂(dpp), M₂(LL')₂(dpp)} (M₁, M₂ = Ru^{II}, Os^{II} or Re^I) are all MLCT-type and the energy of the lowest MLCT excited state increases in the order : Re > Ru > Os. Thus in the binuclear complexes, excitation in the longest wavelength region of the absorption spectrum leads to selective excitation of the lowest energy chromophore, e.g. Os-dpp CT in the case of Ru-dpp-Os and Ru in the case of Ru-dpp-Re. Excitation in the shorter wavelength region leads to excitation of both the high- and low-energy chromophore followed by intramolecular energy transfer from the higher energy one to the lower energy CT excited state as shown below

Chromophore-quencher complexes

An interesting complex we investigated⁶⁹ is the hetero-binuclear complex carrying Ru^{II}- and Rh^{III}-polypyridyl units, [(bpy)₂Ru^{II}-dpp-Rh^{III}(bpy)₂]⁵⁺. We consider the case of long-wavelength excitation of this mixed metal complex, leading to selective excitation of the Ru^{II}-based chromophore (CT excited state),

The higher energy Rh^{III}-polypyridyl fragment can act as a quencher for the following reasons. (i) Rh^{III}-polypyridyl complexes such as Rh(bpy)₃³⁺ and [Rh(bpy)₂Cl₂]Cl are known to be efficient electron-transfer quenchers of the MLCT excited state of Ru^{II}-polypyridyl complexes (reaction 29),

(ii) Polypyridyl complexes of Rh^{III} are known to have their lowest excited state that can be either (π - π^*) or (d - d) type. This is particularly the case with the mixed ligand complexes involving dpp (cf. Fig. 4, for example). The (d , d) state in particular can be sufficiently low in energy to act as an energy-acceptor (reaction 30),

Hence the above complex can be visualised as a chromophore-quencher complex.

Visible light excitation of the mixed metal Rh-dpp-Ru complex leads to formation of the luminescent CT excited state of Ru^{II}-polypyridyl based chromophore. Ru-based emission in the Ru-Rh complex is blue-shifted and short-lived as compared to the model compound Ru-Ru. The very short lifetime of this excited state species in fluid solutions as compared to model compounds can be caused by intramolecular electron transfer or energy transfer quenching (equations 31 and 32 respectively) involving adjacent Rh^{III}-polypyridyl unit. Feasibility of occurrence of these processes can be assessed from a thermodynamic analysis of the energies and redox potentials of the relevant ground and excited states. Analysis of relevant electrochemical and photophysical data in the present case leads to the conclusion that the quenching is primarily by electron transfer (equation 31),

MLCT transitions in cyano-bridged trinuclear complexes

An alternative to polyimine ligands as bridges is to use a bidentate ligand such as cyanide. A number of homo- and mixed-metal cyano-bridged polypyridyl complexes of Re^I and Ru^{II} have been synthesised and their spectroscopic, redox and photophysical properties examined⁷³⁻⁷⁵. Typical examples are [(CO)₃(bpy)Re-CN-Re(bpy)(CO)₃]⁺, [(CO)₃(bpy)Re-NC-Ru(bpy)₂-CN-Re(bpy)(CO)₃]²⁺ and [(CO)₃(bpy)Re-CN-Ru(dcbpy)₂-NC-Re(bpy)(CO)₃]²⁺ (bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine and dcbpy = 4,4'-dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridine). The lowest energy CT excited state in these complexes (Re-bpy or Ru-bpy CT) is emissive in fluid solutions. There have been a number of studies of cyanobridged complexes^{76,77}, especially by Scandola and coworkers.

Using appropriate synthetic procedures it is possible to prepare isomeric complexes of the following type where terminal units are connected to the central units using the cyanide (C-bonded) or isocyanide (N-bonded) mode of linkage :

The C-bonded cyanide is a much better π -acceptor than the N-bonded cyanide and this can be seen in the oxidation potential of the central units in the trinuclear (all Ru-based) complex. A trinuclear Ru-complex of this type used for sensitisation of TiO₂ electrode was mentioned earlier. Studies have shown that the building chromophoric units (-Ru(bpy)₂- and -Re(CO)₃(bpy)-) retain their characteristic properties such as MLCT absorption, emission and redox potentials. These properties however are modified

(‘tuned’) to some extent by intercomponent interactions.

MMCT transitions in cyano-bridged trinuclear complexes

Partial oxidation of the multi-metal centres in polynuclear complexes such as [(CN)(bpy)₂Ru-CN-Ru-NC-Ru(bpy)₂(CN)] gives rise to metal-to-metal charge transfer (MMCT) transitions in the red/near ir region. The MMCT transitions in mixed-valence compounds are also referred to as intervalence (IT) transitions^{78,79}. Monitoring of the IT is an elegant way of probing the extent of electronic coupling between the different metal centres. In the last two decades, there have been a number of studies on the chemistry of mixed valence compounds, particularly on the cyano-bridged systems. The inter-valence transitions in cyanide-bridged systems are known to be much more intense ($\epsilon_{\max} \geq 3000$) than that of the corresponding aromatic polyimine bridged complexes ($\epsilon_{\max} \leq 1000$), reflecting the strong metal-metal electronic coupling in the former complexes⁷⁷.

Fig. 12 (top) shows the absorption spectral changes observed during partial oxidation of the trinuclear complex [(CO)₃(bpy)Re-NC-Ru-CN-Re(CO)₃(bpy)] in acetonitrile using Ce^{IV} as the oxidant. Electrochemical studies have shown that the first oxidation occurs at the central Ru-unit (equation 33),

The formation of the mixed valence compound is accompanied by growth of distinct absorption in the ir region with a maximum at 1358 nm. The IT absorption in the 600–1800 nm region can be fitted to a single gaussian with a maximum at $0.73 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and a bandwidth of $0.31 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$.

With excited states that are M → L charge transfer in character, optical excitation in the CT band creates a hole in the corresponding metal center. Like the chemically oxidised metal center, this transient hole in turn can give rise to inter-valence

Fig. 12. (Top) Absorption spectral changes observed during Ce^{IV} oxidation of the complex [(CO)₃(bpy)Re-NC-Ru-CN-Re(CO)₃(bpy)] in acetonitrile. (Bottom) Transient absorption spectrum of the Re-NC-Ru-CN-Re complex recorded following 530 nm laser pulse excitation in acetonitrile at ambient temperature.

transitions with the adjacent non-oxidised metal centres (equations 34, 35),

Detection of such inter-valence transition bands in the excited state absorption spectra of polynuclear complexes containing MLCT excited states is of much mechanistic interest. Fig. 12 (bottom) shows the transient absorption spectrum in the 550–1150 nm region recorded following excitation of the Re(I)-NC-Ru(II)-CN-Re(I) complex in acetonitrile, following excitation with a 10 ns, 530 nm laser pulse. The transient absorption in the infrared region is assigned to transient formation of mixed valence compounds.

Fig. 13. Schematic representation of excited state electron transfer leading to transient formation of mixed valence compounds.

A schematic representation of the excited state electron transfer leading to transient formation of mixed valence compound is shown in Fig. 13.

The assignment of the transient absorption to an IT is based on the following grounds. (i) It is well known that excitation of polypyridyl complexes of Ru^{II} to the CT excited state, in effect creates an oxidised metal center (Ru^{III}) and a reduced ligand (LL^{-•}). Thus the trinuclear complexes with the central Ru in the CT excited state can be visualised as *transient mixed-valence species* as shown in equation (36),

The mixed valence species can be detected via their IT absorption only during the lifetime of the CT excited state (lifetime of Ru^{III}). Matching decay kinetics of the transient absorption of the ir band (IT) with the emission decay of CT excited state is consistent with such a description. (ii) No such absorption in the near-ir region can be detected in the transient spectra of the parent mononuclear complexes Ru(bpy)₂(CN)₂ or Ru(dcbpy)₂(CN)₂. Observance of inter-valence (IT) transitions require along with Ru^{III}, additional metal centers linked via the cyanide ligand. Analogous situation is observed during chemical oxidation. (iii) Experiments in the presence of quenchers allow differentiation of the transient absorption due to products from that are purely T-T absorption of the excited state.

Similar transient absorption due to mixed valence species has been reported recently⁷⁵ for the ana-

logous trinuclear complexes [(CN)(bpy)₂Ru-CN-Ru(dcbpy)₂-NC-Ru(bpy)₂(CN)] and [(H₂O)(bpy)₂Ru-CN-Ru(dcbpy)₂-CN-Ru(bpy)₂(H₂O)].

Intramolecular energy transfer in cyano-bridged trinuclear complexes

Luminescence and redox properties have been used to assess intramolecular energy/electron transfer processes between the terminal Re^I-polypyridyl and central Ru^{II}-polypyridyl units in the isomeric trinuclear complexes mentioned earlier⁷⁴: [(CO)₃(bpy)Re-NC-Ru(bpy)₂-CN-Re(bpy)(CO)₃]²⁺ and [(CO)₃(bpy)Re-CN-Ru(dcbpy)₂-NC-Re(bpy)₂(CO)₃]²⁺. As in the dpp-bridged complexes, excitation in the visible light region ($\lambda \geq 400$ nm) leads to selective excitation of the central Ru-based chromophore. Irradiation in the near-uv region also causes excitation of the higher energy peripheral Re-based units. The intervalence transitions and the excitation spectra for the Ru-based emission suggest efficient occurrence of energy transfer from the CT excited state of Re-based chromophore to the Ru-based unit in both complexes.

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References

1. Ligand abbreviations used : 2,2'-bipyridine(bpy); 4,4'-dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridine (dcbpy); 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (Me₂bpy); 2,3-bis(2-pyridyl)pyrazine (dpp); 2,2'-biquinoline (biq); dimethylglyoxime (DMG); 2-carboxypyridine (2-COOp); 1,1,2-tetramethylethylenediamine (RMEN); 4,7-dihydroxy-1,10-phenanthroline (DHphen); 3,8-dicarboxy-4,7'-dihydroxy-1,10-phen(DCDIphen); *N,N'*-di-methyl-2,2'-bibenzimidazole (MeBzIm); 2,2'-biimidazole (BiIm); 1,2-bis(2-pyridyl)ethane (BPE); 4,4'-diethylamino-2, 2'-bipyridine(DEAbpy); 2,2-bis(diphenyl)phosphino-1,1'-binaphthyl (BINAP)
2. W. W. BRANDT, F. P. DWYER and E. C. GYARIAS, *Chem Rev.*, 1954, **54**, 959.
3. W. R. MCWHINNIE and J. D. MILLER, *Adv Inorg Chem*

- Radiochem.* 1969, **12**, 135.
4. E. C. CONSTABLE. *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1989, **34**, 1; 1986. **30**, 69.
 5. A. JURIS, F. BARIGELLETTI, V. BALZANI, S. CAMPAGNA, P. BELSER and A. VON ZELEWSKY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1988, **84**, 85.
 6. R. A. KRAUSE, *Struct. Bonding*, 1987, **67**, 1.
 7. T. J. MEYER, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1986, **58**, 1193; M. K. DEARMOND, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1989, **22**, 364.
 8. C. CREUTZ and N. SUTIN, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1980, **52**, 2717.
 9. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **46**, 159.
 10. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, "Photochemistry of Polypyridine and Porphyrin Complexes", Academic, London, 1992.
 11. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, J. KIWI and M. GRATZEL, *Struct. Bonding*, 1982, **49**, 37.
 12. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, M. GRATZEL and E. PELIZZETTI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1986, **69**, 57, and references cited therein.
 13. F. P. ROTZINGER, S. MUNAVALLI, P. COMTE, J. K. HURST, M. GRATZEL, F. H. PERN and A. J. FRANK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **109**, 6619, and references cited therein.
 14. P. LISKA, N. VLACHOPOULOS, MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, P. COMTE and M. GRATZEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 3686.
 15. B. O'REGAN and M. GRATZEL, *Nature*, 1991, **353**, 737.
 16. Md. K. NAZEERUDDIN, P. COMTE, J. MOSER and M. GRATZEL, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1990, **73**, 1788.
 17. Md. K. NAZEERUDDIN and K. KALYANASUNDARAM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 4251.
 18. G. H. ALLEN, R. P. WHITE, D. P. RILLEMA and T. J. MEYER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **106**, 2613; D. P. RILLEMA, G. ALLEN, T. J. MEYER and D. CONRAD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 1617.
 19. J. V. CASPAR, E. M. KOBER, B. P. SULLIVAN and T. J. MEYER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 630; E. M. KOBER, J. L. MARSHALL, W. J. DRESSICK, B. P. SULLIVAN, J. V. CASPAR and T. J. MEYER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 2755; J. V. CASPAR and T. J. MEYER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **83**, 952.
 20. E. M. KOBER, J. V. CASPAR, R. S. LUMPKIN and T. J. MEYER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 3722.
 21. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 2285.
 22. C. T. LIN, W. BOTTCHER, M. CHOU, C. CREUTZ and N. SUTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 6536; C. CREUTZ, M. CHOU, T. L. NETZEL, M. OKAMURA and N. SUTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 1309.
 23. M. J. COOK, A. P. LEWIS, G. S. MCAULIFFE, V. SKARDA, A. J. THOMPSON, J. L. GLASPER and D. J. ROBBINS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.* 2, 1984, 1293, 1303, 1309.
 24. (a) L. DELLA CIANA, W. L. DRESSICK, D. SANDRINI, M. MAESTRI and M. CIANO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 2792; (b) J. V. CASPAR and T. J. MEYER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 2444.
 25. K. KALYANASUNDARAM and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1992, **193**, 292.
 26. M. T. INDELLI, C. A. BIGNOZZI, A. MARCONI and F. SCANDOLA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 7381.
 27. M. NISHIZAWA, T. M. SUZUKI, R. J. WATTS and P. C. FORD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 1837.
 28. M. E. FRINK, S. D. SPROUSE, H. A. GOODWIN, R. J. WATTS and P. C. FORD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 1283.
 29. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, M. GRATZEL and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 5865.
 30. M. T. INDELLI and F. SCANDOLA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 3056.
 31. (a) P. J. GIORDANO, C. R. BOCK, M. S. WRIGHTON, L. V. INTERRANTE and R. F. X. WILLIAMS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 3187; (b) J. FERGUSON, A. W. H. MAU and W. H. F. SASSE, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1979, **68**, 21; (c) T. SHIMIDZU, T. IYODA and K. IZAKI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 642.
 32. R. J. CRUTCHLEY, N. KRESS and A. B. P. LEVER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 1170.
 33. A. KIRSCH DE MESMAEKER, L. JACQUET and J. NASIELSKI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 4451.
 34. K. KALYANASUNDARAM and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1990, **171**, 213.
 35. (a) A. WELLER, *Prog. React. Kinet.*, 1961, **1**, 189; (b) I. F. IRELAND and P. A. II. WYATT, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1976, **12**, 131.
 36. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
 37. G. M. BRYANT and J. E. FERGUSON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 275.
 38. E. M. KOBER and T. J. MEYER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 1614.
 39. R. J. CRUTCHLEY, A. A. SALEH, K. McCAW and M. A. S. AQUINO, *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 1991, **194**, 93.
 40. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN and S. M. ZAKEERUDDIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993 (in press).
 41. (a) Y. OKAMOTO, T. INUKAI and H. C. BROWN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4969; (b) H. C. BROWN and Y. OKAMOTO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4979; (c) J. MARCH, "Advanced Organic Chemistry: Reactions, Mechanisms and Structure", 2nd ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1985.
 42. (a) R. A. MARCUS and N. SUTIN, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1985, **811**, 265; (b) N. SUTIN, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **30**, 441, and references cited therein.
 43. N. S. HUSH, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **8**, 391.
 44. (a) D. REHM and A. WELLER, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 834; *Isr. J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 259.
 45. V. BALZANI and F. SCANDOLA in "Energy Resources Through Photochemistry and Catalysis", ed. M. GRATZEL, Academic, New York, 1983, p. 1.
 46. N. SERPONE in "Photoinduced Electron Transfer", eds. M. A. FOX and M. CHANON, Elsevier, Amsterdam, Part D, 1988, p. 53.
 47. K. KALYANASUNDARAM in "Photosensitization and Photocatalysis using Inorganic and Organometallic Compounds", eds. K. KALYANASUNDARAM and M. GRATZEL, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, Holland, 1993.
 48. "Photochemical Energy Conversion", eds. J. R. NORRIS and D. MEISEL, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1989.

49. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, J. KIWI and M. GEATZEL, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1978, **61**, 2720; A. HARRIMAN and A. MILLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2*, 1981, **77**, 2111.
50. K. KALYANASUNDARAM and M. NEUMANN-SPALLART, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1982, **88**, 7.
51. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, *Nouv. J. Chem.*, 1979, **3**, 511.
52. (a) K. KALYANASUNDARAM and M. GRATZEL, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1979, **18**, 701; (b) K. KALYANASUNDARAM, O. MICIC, E. PRAMAURO and M. GRATZEL, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1979, **62**, 2432.
53. (a) A. HARRIMAN, G. PORTER and P. WALTERS, *J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans. 2*, 1981, **77**, 2373; (b) J. M. LEHN, J.-P. SAUVAGE and R. ZIESSEL, *Nouv. J. Chim.*, 1979, **3**, 423; (c) V. YA. SHAFIROVICH, N. K. KHANNOV and V. V. STRELETS, *Nouv. J. Chim.*, 1980, **4**, 81.
54. M. NEUMANN-SPALLART, K. KALYANASUNDARAM, C. GRATZEL and M. GRATZEL, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **63**, 1111.
55. G. BLONDEEL, A. HARRIMAN, G. PORTER, D. URWIN and J. KIWI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 2629.
56. M. NEUMANN-SPALLART and K. KALYANASUNDARAM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 2681; *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **55**, 704; *J. Chem. Commun.*, 1981, 437.
57. (a) W. J. DRESSICK, T. J. MEYER, B. DURHAM and D. P. RILLEMA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 3451, and references cited therein; (b) G. NEYHART, J. L. MARSHALL, W. J. DRESSICK, B. P. SULLIVAN, P. A. WATKINS and T. J. MEYER, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 915; (c) K. CHANDRASEKARAN and D. G. WHITTEN, *Isr. J. Chem.*, 1982, **22**, 147; (d) A. DERONZIER and F. ESPOSITO, *Nouv. J. Chim.*, 1983, **7**, 15; (e) H. CANO-YELO and A. DERONIZER, *Nouv. J. Chim.*, 1983, 7147, and references cited therein.
58. R. ZIESSEL, *Nouv. J. Chim.*, 1983, **7**, 613.
59. B. P. SULLIVAN, M. R. M. BRUCE, T. R. ÓTOOLE, C. M. BOOLINGER, E. MEGEHEE, H. THORP and T. J. MEYER in "Catalytic Activation of CO₂", ed. W. M. AYER, American Chemical Society, Washington, DC, 1988.
60. R. ZIESSEL in "Photosensitization and Photocatalysis using Inorganic and Organometallic Compound", eds. K. KALYANASUNDARAM and M. GRATZEL, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, Holland, 1993.
61. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2*, 1986, **82**, 2401.
62. C. KUTAL, M. A. WEBER, G. FERRAUDI and D. GEIGER, *Organometallics*, 1985, **4**, 2161; (b) C. KUTAL, A. J. CORBIN and G. FERRAUDI, *Organometallics*, 1987, **6**, 553.
63. F. SCANDOLA, M. T. INDELLI, C. CHIORBOLI and C. A. BIGNOZZI, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1990, **158**, 73.
64. V. BALZANI and F. SCANDOLA, "Supramolecular Photochemistry", Ellis Harwood, Chichester, 1991.
65. R. AMADELLI, R. ARGAZZI, C. A. BIGNOZZI and F. SCANDOLA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 7099.
66. K. KALYANASUNDARAM and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 1888; *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1989, **158**, 45.
67. K. KALYANASUNDARAM and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 1657.
68. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, M. GRATZEL and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1991, 343.
69. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, M. GRATZEL and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 5865.
70. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, M. GRATZEL, MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, R. B. GIRLING and R. F. HESTER, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 323.
71. (a) C. H. BRAUENSTEIN, A. D. BAKER, T. D. STREKAS and H. D. GAFNEY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 857; (b) Y. FUCHI, S. LOFTERS, T. DIETER, W. SHI, R. MORGAN, T. C. STREKAS and H. D. GAFNEY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 269.
72. (a) K. J. BREWER, W. R. MURPHY and J. D. PETERSEN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 3376; (b) A. W. WALLACE, W. R. MURPHY and J. D. PETERSEN, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1989, **166**, 47.
73. (a) G. DENTI, S. CAMPAGNA, L. SABATINO, S. SERRONI, M. CIANO and V. BALZANI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 4750; (b) A. JURIS, S. CAMPAGNA, I. BIDD, J.-M. LEHN and R. ZIESSEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 4007.
74. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, M. GRATZEL and MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 5243.
75. K. MATSUI, MD. K. NAZEERUDDIN, R. HUMPHRY-BAKER, M. GRATZEL and K. KALYANASUNDARAM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 10587.
76. (a) A. VOGLER and H. KUNKELY, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 83; (b) M. NISHIZAWA and P. C. FORD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **27**, 2016.
77. (a) C. A. BIGNOZZI, S. ROFFIA and F. SCANDOLA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 1644; (b) C. A. BIGNOZZI, S. ROFFIA, C. CHIORBOLI, J. DAVILA, M. T. INDELLI and F. SCANDOLA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 4350; (c) C. A. BIGNOZZI, M. T. INDELLI and F. SCANDOLA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 5192; (d) C. A. BIGNOZZI and F. SCANDOLA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 1540.
78. C. CREUTZ, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **30**, 1.
79. M. B. ROBIN and P. DAY, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1967, **10**, 247.

